

ANCIENT ENVIRONMENTALISM AND THE MODERN CLIMATE
CRISIS: A PHILOSOPHICAL AND ETHICAL ANALYSIS IN THE
DISCUSSION OF ANTHROPOCENTRISM TO ECOCENTRISM

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Abstract

In modern society, climate change has emerged as a profound crisis for human civilization. Global warming, rising sea levels, irregular rainfall, and the rapid depletion of natural resources are endangering the environmental balance. Modern technology and developmental activities have, in many cases, failed to mitigate this crisis; rather, they have often intensified the problem. In this context, ancient traditional knowledge systems particularly methods of agriculture, forest conservation, and water management have regained relevance. This research paper analyzes the practices of ancient Indian and other traditional societies to demonstrate that they can play an effective role in tackling the modern climate crisis. The study is based on a qualitative method, employing historical, philosophical, and comparative analysis. The climate crisis has emerged as one of the major challenges to human civilization in the present world. An anthropocentric perspective is identified as a significant cause behind this crisis. This research paper analyzes the relationship between ancient environmental practices such as sustainable agriculture, forest conservation, and water management and the modern climate crisis. Philosophically, it critiques anthropocentrism and discusses biocentric and ecocentric ethics as alternatives. The research aims to prove that ancient environmental knowledge can provide effective guidance in addressing the modern environmental crisis.

Keywords: Water management, agriculture, forest, deep ecology, land ethic, environmental ethics, anthropocentrism, non-violence.

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Introduction:

Climate change is one of the most important problems of our time. Industrialization, urbanization, and excessive use of fossil fuels have disrupted the ecological balance of the earth. This has resulted in an increase in natural disasters, loss of biodiversity, and water shortages. However, to find out solutions to this crisis, modern society has often ignored ancient knowledge systems. In ancient societies, people lived in coexistence relationships with nature. Their methods of agriculture, forestry, and water management were sustainable and environmentally friendly. The main objective of this research is to re-evaluate this traditional knowledge in a modern context and analyze its applicability in addressing the climate crisis. Now the question is how environmentally friendly and sustainable were ancient agricultural methods? How did traditional forest conservation practices protect biodiversity? How are ancient water management practices helpful in addressing modern water crises? How can this traditional knowledge be incorporated into modern environmental policy?

In discussions of environmental ethics, many thinkers have highlighted the inherent value of nature. Arne Naess's Deep Ecology theory recognizes the intrinsic value of nature. Aldo Leopold's Land Ethic concept considers humans as part of the

environment. Indian philosophy views nature as divine, where trees, rivers and mountains are considered sacred. This view provides a moral basis for environmental conservation. Modern research has shown that traditional water conservation methods such as tanks and wells can be effective in addressing the current water crisis.

Main discussion:

Ancient Agricultural Methods:

Ancient agricultural systems were essentially nature based, sustainable and long-term. Unlike modern industrial agriculture, where chemical fertilizers, pesticides and monocultures dominate, ancient agricultural systems ensured production while maintaining environmental balance. These systems were inherently environmentally sensitive, preserving biodiversity and protecting soil fertility. Crop diversity is an important feature of ancient agriculture. Farmers grew multiple crops on the same land, such as cereals, pulses, vegetables, etc. This diversified farming system helped maintain soil nutrients and reduced pest infestation. This eliminated the need for chemical pesticides and made agriculture environmentally friendly. Where modern monoculture systems lead to soil degradation and increased risk of disease, ancient systems provided an alternative. Ancient agriculture preserved the natural qualities of the soil through the use of

organic fertilizers. Cow dung, rotted leaves and other natural materials fertilized the soil and kept the soil biologically active. This improved soil structure and maintained productivity in the long term. In contrast, modern chemical fertilizers damage soil biodiversity and make the soil unfertile in the long run. Crop rotation is a very important strategy of ancient agriculture. After producing a specific crop in one season, a different type of crop was grown in the next season. For example, legumes add nitrogen to the soil, which is beneficial for the next crop. This method maintains the nutrient balance of the soil and controls the spread of pests. Mixed farming and intercropping were widely practiced in ancient agriculture. Growing different crops together can provide one crop. As a result, one crop can provide nutrients or protect another crop. For example, some plants repel pests, while others increase soil fertility. This natural combination makes agriculture more stable. Ancient agriculture emphasized the use of local seeds. Since these seeds are adapted to the local climate and soil, they can be produced with less water and less care. They are more resilient and able to adapt to climate change than modern hybrid seeds. Environmental damage was reduced through the use of natural pesticides. Neem leaves, plant extracts and Pest control was done using

other natural ingredients, which are safe for the environment and human health.

From a philosophical perspective, ancient agricultural methods establish a co-existence of humans with nature. Here, nature is considered not only as a resource, but also as a living entity. This view is consistent with the Deep Ecology theory of environmental ethics, which recognizes the intrinsic value of nature. In the contemporary context, ancient agricultural methods can serve as an effective defense against climate change. Organic farming, diversified farming, and the use of local seeds can reduce carbon emissions, increase soil fertility, and preserve biodiversity. Ancient agricultural methods can be considered not only a historical practice, but also an important foundation for modern sustainable agriculture.

Forest conservation:

ancient societies, forests were not only considered as economic resources, they were also an integral part of religious, cultural and ethical life. This perspective led to forest conservation becoming a spontaneous social practice. In modern times, where deforestation and biodiversity loss are serious problems, ancient forest conservation methods can be considered as an alternative sustainable model. Sacred groves are a notable example of ancient forest conservation. There were some forests in various parts of the world, including

India, that were completely reserved for religious beliefs. Cutting, hunting or other exploitative activities were prohibited in these forests. As a result, they played an important role as a haven for biodiversity. From an ecological perspective, sacred groves functioned as a kind of micro-reserve, where rare plants and animals were preserved. Community based forest management was very effective in ancient societies. Local people considered the forests as their own resources and were responsible for their maintenance. This system had social control over forest use, which prevented overexploitation. This system was more participatory than modern centralized forest management. Limited and controlled use was an important feature of ancient forest management. People collected necessary resources from the forest, but never exceeded the regenerative capacity of nature. For example, collecting dry wood, using medicinal plants and cutting down small amounts of wood these activities were carried out without disturbing the balance of the environment. In ancient societies, the relationship between forests and religious beliefs played an important role in forest conservation. Many trees and woodlands were considered the abodes of gods. As a result, destroying forests was not only considered an environmental, but also a moral and religious crime. This moral control served as a strong social motivation

for forest conservation. Conservation of biodiversity was an inherent goal of ancient forest management. Different species of plants and animals were allowed to coexist, which created a stable ecosystem. Whereas modern deforestation and monoculture weaken ecosystems, the ancient system maintained environmental stability.

Philosophically, these forest conservation methods were based on a holistic view. Here, people considered themselves not as masters of nature, but as a part of it. This idea is consistent with the theories of Land Ethic and Deep Ecology in environmental ethics, where the unique value of nature is recognized. In the contemporary context, it is very important to revive these traditional forest conservation methods. These techniques can be helpful in reducing the impact of current deforestation and climate change. However, there are also some limitations, such as population growth, modern economic pressures and commercial use of land. Therefore, it is necessary to combine modern policies and technologies rather than directly applying ancient methods. Ancient forest conservation traditions are not only cultural heritage, but also an effective ecological strategy, which can play an important role in addressing the modern climate crisis.

Water management methods:

Water is a natural resource essential for the existence of human civilization. Water deficiency has emerged as a serious environmental and social problem in the world today. This crisis has been exacerbated by climate change, overuse of groundwater, and uncontrolled urbanization. In this context, traditional methods of ancient water management deserve to be re-evaluated as an effective and alternative. Water management in ancient societies was in harmony with the local environment, geography, and climate. These methods were developed through long experience and observation and ensured the sustainable use of natural resources. Rainwater conservation is an important aspect of ancient water management. People Rainwater was collected and stored and used as per the requirement. Various structures were constructed on the roofs of houses, open spaces to collect water. This reduced the pressure on groundwater and ensured water supply during droughts. Wells and reservoir systems were prevalent in ancient Indian society. These structures were used not only as a source of water but also as social and cultural centres. The special design of the wells helped in maintaining the water level and made it possible to store water even during summer. Similarly, water was stored in rural areas by constructing tanks, ponds and artificial reservoirs. Local water

management is a fundamental feature of the ancient system. Water management strategies were determined according to the geographical and climatic features of different regions. Controlling water flow in hilly areas, building reservoirs in plains and storing rainwater in dry areas. These diverse methods ensured efficient management of water resources. The local people ensured the maintenance, cleaning and proper use of water bodies. Groundwater recharge is an important aspect of the ancient system. Rainwater used to infiltrate the ground through ponds, canals, and reservoirs to replenish groundwater levels. This method is extremely relevant in modern times, where groundwater levels are rapidly declining due to excessive pumping.

From a philosophical perspective, ancient water management reflects an integrated and ethical perspective on water conservation. Water was not only considered a resource, but rather a source of life. This perspective morally compelled people to avoid wasting it. It is imperative to revive these traditional methods in the present day. These water conservation strategies can be effective in addressing the current water crisis and the impacts of climate change. However, there are some limitations – such as urbanization, population growth, and lack of modern infrastructure. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an integrated water system by combining ancient methods with

modern technology. The tradition of ancient water management is not just a cultural practice of the past, but a solution for the present and the future. Re-evaluation and application of these methods is essential to address the climate crisis.

Philosophical perspective:

The true significance of ancient agricultural, forestry and water management methods cannot be fully understood by analyzing them from a purely practical or technical perspective. Deep within these practices lies a coherent philosophical foundation that redefines the relationship between humans and nature. This philosophical analysis provides an important perspective for understanding the modern environmental crisis. In ancient traditional knowledge systems, nature is considered an entity with inherent value, which creates a fundamental contrast with the modern utilitarian perspective. In modern industrial societies, nature is primarily seen as a means to meet human needs, where its value is determined by its utility. In contrast, ancient Indian philosophical thought recognized nature as self-sufficient and with a distinct dignity. By considering trees, rivers, mountains and other natural elements as symbols of divinity, a deep sense of respect and moral responsibility for nature has been developed. This perspective establishes humans as protectors of nature, not exploiters, and makes environmental

conservation a moral duty. As a result, this ancient, intrinsic value-based perspective provides an important theoretical foundation for modern environmental ethics, which can be considered an alternative moral framework for addressing the climate crisis.

Holism is reflected as a fundamental tenet in ancient philosophical thought, where humans, animals, plants, and the environment are considered to be an interdependent and inseparable entity. According to this view, no part of nature is the loss of one component affects the entire ecosystem. Modern environmental crises such as biodiversity loss, climate change, and soil degradation are the result of underestimating these interrelationships. The practical application of this holistic thinking can be seen in ancient agricultural, forest conservation, and water management methods, where balance was maintained between the various components of nature. This perspective is consistent with the modern concept of ecosystem-based management and provides a useful theoretical framework for development. Therefore, holism is not just a philosophical concept, but a pragmatic policy that ensures an integrated and long-term approach to environmental conservation.

In ancient environmental ethics, the concept of non-violence is considered a

central principle, calling for non-violent behavior towards all living beings and nature. This principle is not limited to human relations; rather, it applies to animals, plants, and the entire environment. In ancient societies, the use of natural resources was controlled and moderated, so as not to create unnecessary pressure on nature. This ethical perspective is consistent with the principle of non-harm in modern environmental ethics. In the current context, where excessive consumerism and indiscriminate use of resources are intensifying the environmental crisis, the principle of non-violence provides an important alternative perspective. It motivates people to behave responsibly towards the environment and leads to a sustainable lifestyle. In ancient philosophical traditions, the concept of religion provides a fundamental ethical framework for environmental protection. Here, religion is not limited to religious behavior or rituals, but is a comprehensive ethical provision that directs the maintenance of a balanced relationship between the individual, society, and nature. In ancient Indian thought, humans are considered the guardians of nature, whose responsibility is to maintain the balance of the environment and ensure the moderate use of natural resources. This view establishes environmental conservation not as an optional activity, but as a moral duty. In modern environmental ethics, this

concept is similar to environmental responsibility. Especially in the context of climate change, where the human centered development model has placed excessive pressure on the environment, this religiously based moral framework can guide people towards responsible and moderate behavior.

Important theories of modern environmental ethics, especially Deep Ecology and Land Ethic, have deep similarities with ancient philosophical perspectives. Deep Ecology theory recognizes the intrinsic value of nature and opposes the anthropocentric hegemonic perspective. According to this theory, humans are not dominators of nature, but rather part of a larger biosphere. Similarly, the Land Ethic concept considers humans as members of a biotic community, where morality is not limited to humans but also extends to soil, plants and animals. Such a perspective has long existed in ancient Indian knowledge systems, where coexistence and interdependence between humans and nature were recognized. This theoretical parallelism proves that ancient traditional knowledge can be considered not only a cultural legacy, but also an important intellectual foundation for modern environmental ethics. One of the characteristics of modern development is anthropocentrism, which considers nature as an instrument for the fulfilment of

human interests. This perspective has led to indiscriminate exploitation of natural resources, deforestation and ecological imbalances. Ancient philosophical thought presents a fundamental critique of this anthropocentric tendency and replaces it with a biocentric or nature-centric perspective. According to this view, all living things have their own value and are not dependent on humans for their existence. Consequently, environmental protection is essential not only for human benefit, but also for the well-being of the entire biosphere. This perspective is particularly important in the context of the current climate crisis. Because it makes people aware of their limitations and calls for establishing a balanced relationship with nature.

However, these philosophical perspectives also have some limitations. The populations of ancient societies were small and their lifestyles were relatively simple, which made these approaches effective. It is difficult to directly apply these perspectives to modern complex societies. Therefore, an integrated approach is needed, where ancient moral values and modern scientific knowledge work together. There is a strong philosophical basis behind ancient traditional methods of agriculture, forest conservation and water management, which can provide new perspectives to address modern environmental crises. This

perspective helps us to rethink our relationship with nature and move towards a just future.

Application in modern time:

In the current world, climate change, environmental pollution, biodiversity loss and water scarcity have together created a complex global crisis. In this situation, modern technology-based solutions alone are not enough; rather, an integrated approach is needed, where a creative dialogue is established between ancient traditional knowledge and modern scientific methods. In this context, ancient agricultural, forest conservation and water management methods can play an important role in contemporary environmental management. The application of ancient agricultural methods in the development of agricultural concepts in contemporary agricultural systems is particularly significant. While modern industrial agriculture is dependent on high levels of chemical fertilizers, pesticides and monoculture, ancient agricultural methods show an alternative way to ensure production while maintaining ecological balance. Practices such as crop diversification, cyclical agriculture and the use of organic fertilizers play an important role in preserving soil fertility, protecting biodiversity and reducing carbon emissions. In addition, the use of local seeds increases the ability of agriculture to adapt to climate

change. Currently, this ancient knowledge is being revived through the organic farming and agroecology movements, which on the one hand ensure food security, and on the other hand help maintain environmental stability. As a result, the re-evaluation and application of ancient methods in agriculture can be considered an effective solution to the modern agricultural crisis.

Community based forest management is being established as an effective and sustainable model in contemporary environmental conservation, which has its roots in ancient forest conservation traditions. In ancient societies, the participatory forest management practices of local people ensured the balanced use of forest resources. In the current context, involving local people in forest management through participatory governance makes it possible to prevent deforestation, conserve biodiversity, and maintain ecological balance. Especially in developing countries, where local people's livelihoods depend on forest resources, this method is able to strike a balance between environmental conservation and social justice. Decentralized water management is being considered a very effective strategy to address the contemporary water crisis, which is a modern form of ancient water conservation methods. Rainwater conservation, local reservoir construction, and groundwater recharge processes can

play an important role in solving today's water crisis. Especially where natural water flows are being disrupted due to urbanization, rainwater harvesting and local water management methods help ensure the balanced use of water resources. This method is sustainable not only from an environmental perspective, but also economically.

Ancient traditional knowledge can make an important contribution to increasing climate resilience. Ancient agricultural practices, such as the use of drought-tolerant local seeds and water conservation techniques, increase the ability to adapt to natural changes. This adaptability is very important in the current context of climate change, as it stabilizes agricultural production and ensures food security. As a result, ancient knowledge-based practices can serve as an effective adaptation strategy to deal with the impacts of climate change. The inclusion of ancient knowledge systems in contemporary policymaking and environmental governance is very necessary. If local knowledge, traditional experiences and people's participation are given importance in modern environmental policies, they can be more realistic and effective. Adopting a bottom-up approach instead of a top-down approach increases local responsibility for environmental conservation and makes policy implementation more successful. The

moral and philosophical influence of ancient traditions can play an important role in developing sustainable lifestyles in contemporary societies. While modern consumerist culture encourages excessive consumption of resources, ancient views teach moderation, coexistence, and respect for nature. This moral foundation motivates people to behave responsibly towards the environment and helps establish a long-term sustainable society.

According to Ramachandra Guha, ancient environmental knowledge and the explanation of modern crises:

Ramachandra Guha, in his environmental historical analysis, shows that ancient Indian environmentalism was not just a practical method, but was part of a moral and cultural consciousness. In particular, the tradition of considering forests, rivers and land as sacred strengthened the concept of respect and responsibility for nature. This view is consistent with the concept of intrinsic value in modern environmental ethics, where nature is considered not only as an object of human use, but also as an entity with its own value. Therefore, according to Guha, re-evaluating ancient environmental knowledge does not mean simply reviving tradition, but also finding an alternative moral framework. At the same time, Guha criticizes colonial forest policy, showing that when forests were declared as state

resources during British rule, the traditional rights of local people were violated. As a result, the interdependent relationship between people and nature was broken and an exploitative structure was established. In this context, environmental destruction is not just an environmental problem, but also a social and moral crisis. Guha's analysis here clearly indicates that the modern development model is actually a form of anthropocentric hegemony, which creates environmental inequality. Guha's concept of Environmentalism of the Poor is analyzed more deeply and it is seen that it provides an alternative framework to the conventional elite environmentalism. Whereas elite or urban-centric environmentalism mainly views conservation from an aesthetic or scientific perspective, the environmental movement of the poor is inextricably linked to the necessity of survival. Movements like the Chipko Movement highlight this reality, where environmental protection is not an abstract policy, but part of the struggle for survival. From this perspective, Guha also brings up the question of environmental justice.

Philosophically, Guha's thought provides a clear critique of anthropocentrism and calls for a move towards an eco-centric ethic. According to him, if environmental conservation is to be effective, technological solutions alone are

not enough, but social justice, recognition of local knowledge and ethical reframing are needed. In this context, ancient environmental practices offer an important direction that can help build a sustainable and inclusive path to confronting the modern climate crisis. Ramachandra Guha shows in his eco-historical analysis, that ancient Indian environmentalism was not just a practical method, but was part of a moral and cultural consciousness. In particular, the tradition of considering forests, rivers and land as sacred reinforced the idea of respect and responsibility for nature. This view is consistent with the concept of intrinsic value in modern environmental ethics, where nature is considered not only as an object of human use, but also as an entity with its own value. Therefore, according to Guha, re-evaluating ancient environmental knowledge does not mean simply reviving traditions, but also finding an alternative moral framework. At the same time, Guha criticizes colonial forest policy, showing that when forests were declared as state resources during British rule, the traditional rights of local people were violated. As a result, the interdependent relationship between people and nature was broken and an exploitative structure was established. In this context, environmental destruction is not only an environmental problem, but also a social and moral crisis. Guha's analysis here clearly

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Conclusion:

The discussion in this paper shows that the modern climate crisis is not just a natural problem, but is essentially a

philosophical and moral crisis, with an anthropocentric perspective at its core. The tendency to view nature as an object of human utility has legitimized the overexploitation of natural resources, resulting in environmental imbalances. Ramachandra Guha's analysis is particularly significant in this context, as he shows that in ancient environments, the relationship between humans and nature was based on mutual dependence and moral responsibility. Ancient environmental methods, such as the conservation of sacred forests, local water management, and sustainable agriculture, recognize the inherent value of nature and reflect a non-anthropocentric moral framework. In contrast, modern industrialization and development-oriented policies have broken this relationship, accelerating environmental destruction and the climate crisis. Movements like the Chipko Movement demonstrate that local communities and ancient knowledge can still play an effective role in environmental conservation. This research clearly shows that technological innovation alone is not enough to solve the climate crisis permanently, but requires a fundamental moral restructuring, moving away from anthropocentrism to an eco-centric and biocentric perspective. In this process, it is essential to incorporate ancient environmental knowledge into modern policymaking. Combining ancient knowledge

and modern science is the only effective way to build a just, sustainable and environmentally sensitive future. In ancient Indian society, the environment was not only seen as a resource, but also as an integral part of life and a moral entity. was considered. Conservation of sacred forests, construction of reservoirs, rainwater harvesting and organic farming, all these practices recognize the inherent value of nature and reflect an eco-centric ethic. Ancient environmental practices are not just historical memories, but a realistic and relevant guide to confronting the modern climate crisis. Building a just and sustainable future requires a fundamental change in human perspective, where humans see themselves not as masters of nature, but as a part of it. Reconstructing this perspective is the core teaching of ancient environmental practices and a guide to possible solutions to the modern climate crisis.

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